

EFFECT OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF ENGLISH STUDENTS IN SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS, OKENE, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study investigates the effect of instructional materials on the performance of English students in selected secondary schools in Okene, Kogi State, Nigeria. The study aims to determine whether the use of instructional materials enhances students' understanding and performance in English language. The study adopted descriptive survey research design as opinions of the respondents were sought on their perception about the utilization of instructional materials in ensuring effective teaching and learning. A sample of 104 respondents comprising teachers and students from selected secondary schools in Okene, Kogi State, participated in the study. Data were collected through questionnaire. Findings shows that instructional materials have a positive impact on students' performance in English language. The findings equally suggest that teachers should incorporate instructional materials into their teaching practices to enhance students' understanding and academic achievement. The following recommendations were offered: School administration should ensure that instructional materials are provided for teachers to enhance effective teaching of English; teachers and students should form the habit of improvising instructional materials to make up the shortfall in supply; teachers should apply special knowledge and skills with respect to selecting, producing and using different kinds of instructional materials; enough time should be allotted in the schools' time table for effective use of instructional materials in English classroom; a committee should be set up in educational sector to monitor teachers use of instructional materials in teaching English; and, educational managers should ensure that English teachers have educational qualification in English as a way of acquainting them with the principle and administration of instructional materials in secondary schools.*

Introduction

Language is a means of communications by which human beings interact and exchange their thoughts, ideas and feelings. In agreement. Anagbogu. Mba and Ene (2002), defined

language as, "a means devised by human beings for communicating sdeus, feelings emotions, and desires, through complex vocal or written symbols Language is, therefore, an indispensable tool in any human society. Nwaozuzu (2008)

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

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referred to language as one of the most fundamental aspects of human behavior. Though language is universal in human society, every society is associated with one or more languages. The colonial masters introduced the English language (12) due to the multilingual nature of the nation and it helps in the unification of the nation. English language was considered as the only official means of instruction in training people to serve in the government and as well it become Nigeria's lingual Franca. That is, language of convenience for communication with diverse ethnic groups in Nigeria and an indispensable tool for national unity, integration and global communication.

Today, English language has been made compulsory and all levels of the school system. English language as a course or subject holds the key to further academic progress in Nigeria, in order to have the opportunity to study any course in the university, polytechnic, or college of education, a candidate must have obtained a credit pass in the West African School certificate Examination or its equivalents. English language is the medium of instruction at all levels of educational institution. The purpose of instructional materials is to promote efficiency of education by improving the quality of teaching and learning. Incorporation of these tools and materials present, support and reinforce reaching. According to Aduwa-Ogiegbean and Imogie (2005), these materials and resources including audio tape recorders, videos tapes recorders slide projector opaque projectors, overhead projectors, still picture, programmed

institution, film strips, maps, charts, graphs and many more offer a variety of leaning experience individually or in combination to meet different learning experiences.

Based on the assertions above, the researches intend to investigate the effects of the use of instructional materials on the academic performance of students in English language in selected secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Statement of the Problem

The study and mastery of English language is a major objective of Nigeria educational systems. The achievement of this objective requires the concern of both the government and private owners of schools in collaboration with classroom teachers. There is a need for proper prevision and utilization of instructional materials in order to achieve the objective of the emphasis laid on the teaching and learning of English language at all educational levels provision and improvisation of instructional materials and proper utilization in delivering English language lessons, undoubtedly, improves the teaching and learning outcome of the subject.

Despite the concert on the importance and place of instructional materials in teaching and learning English language, there is a glaring absence of these materials and poor utilization by teachers. The resultant effects of the absence of instructional materials and poor utilization on students include mass failure in English language examination in secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State, as

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well as poor grammar in written and spoken aspects.

However, because of the problem of mass failure in English language in secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State, the researcher intend to investigate the effect of the use of instructional materials on the academic performance of students in English language in Okene Local Government Area in Kogi State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of the use of instructional materials on academic performance of students in English language. Specifically, the study tends to:

- i. Determine the availability of instructional materials and resources for the teaching of English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.
- ii. Ascertain the extent of teachers' use of instructional materials in the process of teaching English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.
- iii. Evaluate extent to which the use of instructional materials in teaching English language have contribute to the academic excellence of the secondary school students in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.
- iv. Identify the significance of instructional materials on the academic performance of students in English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.
- v. Know how English is better taught with the aids of instructional material in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.

vi. Examine the positive impact in the academic performance of students as a result of the presence or use of instruction materials in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Research Questions

The Followings research questions are to guide the Study:

- i. How available are instructional materials and resources for the teaching of English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State?
- ii. To what extend does teachers use instructional materials in the process of teaching English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State?
- iii. To what extent does the use of instructional materials in teaching English language contribute to the academic excellence of the secondary school students in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State?
- vii. What is the significance of instructional materials on the academic performance of students in English language in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.
- iv. How is English better taught with the aids of instructional material in Okene Local Government Area, of Kogi State?
- viii. What is the positive impact in the academic of students as a result of the presence or use of instruction materials in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Significance of the Study

The use of instructional materials gives the learner opportunity to touch, smell or taste objects in the teaching and learning process. The knowledge passed unto the pupils at different

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levels of educational system should be well planned, administered and properly aligned with relevant instructional materials, clarity and comprehensibility to the learners. Hence, this study will be significant to the students, teachers, curriculum planners, educational system, the government and the society at large in the following ways:

Students: It will help to arouse the interest of the students and as well as help them acquire skills in English language, learn effectively and retain what they have learnt thereby, advance their performance in English Language.

Teachers: It will equip teachers with some useful information on the need for effective utilization of instructional materials and as well help them to identify the appropriate instructional materials to be used in teaching and learning English Language and how to use them.

Curriculum planners: It will provide the curriculum planners with some useful information which will make them appreciate the need to work out effective means of providing the essential instructional and materials for the Secondary Schools.

Educational system: It will serve as a good reference document to the educational system.

Government: It will be beneficial to the government at various levels in policy making and execution concerning curriculum development and implementation.

Society: It will benefit the society at large by ensuring effective teaching and learning which will have a lasting positive effect on students at the secondary schools level in particular, and

presecondary and post-secondary school levels in general.

Scope of the Study

The study is an empirical examination of the effect of instructional materials on the academic performance of students in English language in selected secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State. The respondents for the study comprised of teachers and students of the study area. The study is limited to five senior secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State. The schools were selected with the criteria of three (3) government established schools and two private schools. The objectives and significance of the study is clearly stated in chapter one. Chapter two which is the literature review, anchors the importance of instructional materials, use and utilization of instructional materials and other concepts. The study covers 2024/2025 academic session of the study areas.

Definition of Operational Terms

Academic performance: It is the school evaluation of pupil's classrooms work as quantified on the basis of marks.

Effect: A change which is a result or consequence of an action or other cause.

Instructional materials: Is the materials that teachers use in teaching to make the lesson active, interesting, real and understandable to the students.

Students: A person who is studying at educational institution especially at secondary school level or higher institution such as College of Education, Polytechnic, or the University.

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Review of Related Literature

Despite the use of English language, the standard of English language in Nigeria is gradually waning, some of the factors that effective study of English language are mother tongue interference, inadequate use or non-availability of instructional materials and lack of qualification or experienced English language teacher these factor go hand in hampering the effective study of English language in our secondary schools. It is apparent that candidates' performance in English language is not sufficiently sound to equip them for further studies at the tertiary level.

However, for effective teaching and learning of English language in secondary schools as well for academic excellence of students in English language, the relevant instructional materials should be available and adequately used by teachers. Educational technology cannot be ruled out as an instructional innovation. Instructional materials have been essential tools in English language lesson as well as tools for student to attain academic excellence in the course. The materials and sources used for developing the desired knowledge, skills, attitudes and values in students are regarded within the scope of teaching material (Paykoc, 1991; Simsek, 2003). Instructional materials allow students to interact with words, images and ideas in ways and using media as well as other technologies.

The need for tools as well as teaching aids has been discovered quite early in the history of mankind. Before the invention of reading and

writing, parents taught their children using tools. For instance, hunters hunted with bows and arrows, sewed with needles and thread; did furniture work with saws, nails, hammers and others. Sometimes explanations are not needed or necessary if the tools were used to demonstrate the given task. The teachers soon discovered that the use of instructional materials lessened the task of detailed explanation and made reaching less cumbersome more effective and interesting. However, instructional materials are important to clarify concepts, make abstract teaching concrete, real, and spice up the teaching process. It is therefore an understatement to say teaching can be effective without tools. The need to use teaching tools is perhaps more acute in the teaching of English language.

Amadi (1990) term teaching tools as, "instructional resource". He went on to categorize them into three:

- i. Human resources: which could be guests incited to give talks such as persons from school or community.
- ii. Materials resources: which could be used directly with learners in teaching situations such as visual, auditory and audio-visual aids.
- iii. Phenomenal: which are natural events that may relate to one or more aspects of the curriculum such as religion, social, political or economic events. Therefore, instructional materials in the English language should align with the general philosophy of the school, the curriculum, goals and objectives of English

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language and the intended learning outcomes of the subject.

Osakwo and Hediery (1993) summarized these resources as textual, like books, audiovisual and human resources. They state that these resources are either used individually or collectively in any meaningful English language teaching and learning situation which motivates the students to perform well in the subject.

Methodology

The methodology adopted for this research work in primary and secondary method of gathering data or information. The primary data consist of questionnaire, and observation which were designed by the researcher to elicit adequate information from respondents and result of findings that emanated from the analysis of the data were presented in chapter four. The secondary data are information from books, internet, write up, magazines and other relevant publications. Data was analyzed based on the findings through the use of questionnaire and presented using tables.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This chapter is concerned with the presentation and analysis of data collected from the respondents.

Response Rate

This analysis is based on one hundred and eight (108) copies of questionnaire administered out, in which one hundred and four (104) of the questionnaire were retrieved. This is because the one hundred and four (104) were properly filled, but four (4) were either wrongly filled, mutilated or left unfilled rendering the copies invalid. 90 copies of questionnaire were distributed to students and 18 copies to the teachers of English Language. For this study, 86 and 18 copies of questionnaire were returned by students and teachers respectively.

The data collected was divided into three sections: Section A deals with data of schools used for this study. Section B: Students demographic data and responses. Section C: Teachers demographic data and responses. The retrieved questionnaires were processed or analysis using frequency and percentage.

SECTION A

Table 1: Analysis of schools used for the study.

S/N	NAME OF SCHOOLS	FREQUENCY	%	RETRIEVED FREQUENCY	%
1.	Okene High School, Okene	18	16.7	18	17.3
2.	Muslim College, Okene	18	16.7	17	16.3
3.	Government Secondary School, Okene	18	16.7	16	15.4
4.	Adavize High School, Okene	18	16.7	17	16.3
5.	Best Time Group of School, Otutu, Okene	18	16.7	18	17.3
	Total	108	100	104	99.9

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table shows that, 18 copies of questionnaire representing 16.7% copies were distributed to each school. 18 representing 17.3% copies were retrieved from Okene High School, Okene; 17 representing 16.3% were retrieved from Muslim College, Okene; 16 representing 15.4% were retrieved from Government Secondary School,

Okene; 17 representing 16.3 were retrieved from Adavize High School, Okene; and 18 representing 17.3% were collected back from Best Time Group of School, Otutu, Okene. Therefore, the total number of the retrieved questionnaires is one hundred and four (104) representing 99,9%.

Section B: Students' Demographic Data and Responses **Table 2:** Analysis of gender of the respondents.

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Male	38	44.2
Female	48	55.8
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

This shows that 38 respondents representing 44.2% are male while 48 respondents representing 55.8% are female.

Table 3: Classes of the respondents

CLASS	FREQUENCY	PERCNETAGE %
SS ONE	24	27.9
SS TWO	37	43.0
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table shows that, 24 respondents representing 27.9% are in SS one, 37 respondents

representing 43.0% are in SS two while 25 representing 29.1% respondents are in SS three,

Table 4: Age of the respondents.

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
13-17 years	77	89.5
18-21years	9	10.5
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Indicating 77 respondents representing 89.5% are within 13-17 years while respondents

representing 10.5% are within the age of 18-21 years.

Students Responses

Table 5: Analysis of teachers using of charts, chalkboard textbooks in teaching English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCNETAGE %
Yes	75	87.2
No	11	12.7
Total	86	99.9

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table shows that 75 respondents representing 87.2% agree while 11 respondents

representing 12.7% disagree that teachers use charts, chalkboard and textbooks in teaching English:

Table 6: How instructional materials boost the cognitive abilities of students,

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	70	81.4
No	16	18.6
Total	86	100

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Source: Field Survey, 2025 when used for classroom instruction boost their cognitive abilities while 16 respondents representing 18.6% disagree. Showing that, 70 respondents representing 81.4% agreed that chalkboard, chats, tape recorders

Table 7: How instructional materials make learning easy lively and concrete.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	79	91.9
No	7	8.1
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025 instructional materials makes learning easy, lively and concrete while 7 respondents representing 8.1% disagreed with the view. The table above shows that 79 respondents representing 91.9% agreed that usage of

Table 8: How instructional materials enhance students' acquisition and retention of factual information in English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	79	91.9
No	7	8.1
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025 is enhanced learning through instructional materials while 7 respondents representing 8.1% disagreed. The table above shows that. 79 respondents representing 91.99% agreed that their acquisition and retention of factual information

Table 9: How illustration through instructional materials improve students' knowledge toward a topic.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	77	89.5
No	9	10.5
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025 chalkboard, textbooks and pictures improve their knowledge toward a topic in English while 9 respondents representing 10.5% disagreed. The table shows 77 respondents representing 89.5% said illustration through charts,

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Table 10: How students enjoy studying with instructional materials.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	78	
No	8	9.3
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above indicated 78 representing 90.7% respondents support that they enjoy studying tenses, concord, essay writing, passage reading

and oral in English through charts, chalkboard, textbooks while 8 representing 9.3% respondents oppose.

Table 11: Analysis of if instructional materials is a waste of time and complicate learning.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	17	19.8
No	69	80.2
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

In the table above 17 respondents representing 19.8% agreed that use of chalkboard, charts,

textbooks, picture in teaching English is a waste of time and complicate their learning. While 69 respondents representing 80.2% disagreed.

Table 12: The improvement of instructional materials on students writing and speaking skills.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	71	82.6
No	15	17.4
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above shows 71 respondents representing 82.6% agreed that the use of charts, chalkboard, textbooks and pictures improve

their writing and speaking skills while 15 representing 17.4% respondents said instructional materials bring no change in the writing and speaking skills.

Table 13: How teacher's competence determines students' performance in English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Strongly agreed	40	46.5
Agreed	30	34.9
Strongly disagreed	10	11.6

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Disagreed	6	6.9
Total	86	99.9

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 40 respondents representing 46.5% strongly agreed that teacher's competence in English determines

their performance, 30 respondents representing 34.9% agreed, 0 representing 11.6% respondents while 6.9% respondents representing 6 disagreed.

Table 14: students' better performance in any English examination with the sits of instructional materials.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Strongly Agreed	34	39.5
Agreed	40	46.5
Strongly disagreed	3	3.5
Disagreed	9	10.5
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

This table above shows 34 respondents representing 39.5% strongly agreed that they perform better in any English examination when

instructional materials are used; 40 respondents representing 46.5% agreed; 3.5% respondents representing 3 strongly disagreed while 10.5% respondents representing 9 disagreed.

SECTION C: Teachers Demographic Data and Responses

Table 15: Distribution based on Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Male	8	44.4
Female	10	55.6
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that respondents representing 44.4% are male 1 respondents representing 55.6% are female

Table 16: Analysis of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
30-40 years	8	44.4
41-50	7	38.9
51-60	3	16.7

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Total	18	100
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Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above shows that 8 respondents representing 44.4% are within the age of 30-40

years, 38.9% respondents representing 7 are between 41-50 years while 3 representing 16.7% respondents are within the age of 51-60 years.

Table 17: Distribution based on Job Experiences.

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
1-5	3	16.7
6-10	4	22.2
11-15	5	27.8
16 years and above	6	33.3
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 3 respondents representing 16.7% have job experiences of 1-5 years, 22.2% respondents representing 4 have 6-

10 years experiences, 27.85% respondents representing 5 have 11-15 years experiences while 6 representing 33.3% respondents are 16 years and above experience.

Teachers Responses

Table 18: Availability of laboratory or audio tape for teaching oral English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	6	33.3
No	12	66.7
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table shows that 6 respondents representing 33.3% said there is laboratory or audio tape in

teaching oral English while 12 representing 66.7% respondents said laboratory or audio tape is not available for teaching oral English.

Table 19: Availability of charts, chalkboard and textbooks, for searching tenses, passage reading and essay writing

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	15	83.3
No	3	16.
Total	18	100

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

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Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 15 respondents representing 83.3% agreed that charts, chalkboard, textbooks are available for teaching

tenses, concord, passage reading, and essay writing while 3 respondents representing 16.7% disagreed.

Table 20: Availability of models, pictures and real objects for teaching English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	12	66.7
No	6	33.7
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table indicates that 12 representing 66.7% respondents agreed that models, pictures and

real objects are available for teaching English while 6 respondents representing 33.3% disagreed.

Table 21: How instructional materials are used in teaching English.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Often	8	44.4
Sparingly	10	55.6
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table 21 above shows that, 8 respondents representing 44.4% always use instructional

materials while 55.6% respondents representing 10 sparingly use instructional materials.

Table 22: How instructional materials enhance students' acquisition and retention.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	12	66.7
No	6	33.3
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table indicates 12 respondents representing 66.7% agreed with the view that instructional materials enhance students'

acquisition and retention of factual information in English while 6 representing 33.3% respondents disagreed.

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Table 23: How instructional materials make teaching activities lively, easy and concrete

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	15	83.3
No	3	16.7
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 23 above shows that 15 respondents representing 83.3% said teaching with instructional materials is lively, easy and

concrete while 3 respondents representing 16.7% said no.

Table 24: Teachers' interest in teaching English with chalkboard, charts, and textbooks.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	13	72.2
No	5	27.8
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows 13 respondents representing 72.2% enjoy teaching English with

charts, chalkboard, textbooks, etc. while 5 respondents representing 27.8% does not enjoy teaching English with instructional materials.

Table 25: How teachers' competence determines improvement of classroom instruction.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	11	61.1
No	7	38.9
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

This table shows that 11 respondents representing 61.1% agreed that improvement of

English classroom instruction depends on the teacher's competence while 7 respondents representing 38.9 disagreed.

Table 26: Improvements of English classroom instructions depend on teacher's competence and instructional materials.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	13	72.2
No	5	27.8
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 13 respondents representing 72.2% agreed that improvement of

Table 27: Pupils taught English with instructional materials perform excellently in wo English examination than those taught with traditional method.

classroom instruction depends on teacher's competence and instructional materials while 5 respondents representing 27.8% disagreed.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Strongly agreed	6	33.3
Agreed	10	55.6
Strongly agreed	0	0
Disagreed	2	11.1
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 6 respondents representing 33.3% strongly agreed that pupils taught tenses, concord, essay writing, oral and passage reading with instructional materials

Table 28: Pupils taught English with traditional or oral method hardly have credit pass.

perform excellently than those taught with conventional method; 10 representing 55.6 respondents agreed while 2 respondents representing 11.1% disagree.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Strongly agreed	4	22.2
Agreed	12	66.7
Strongly agreed	0	0
Disagreed	2	11.1
Total	18	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table shows that 4 respondents representing 22.2% strongly agreed that pupils taught tenses, concord essay writing, passage reading and only with conventional method will hardly have credit pass in any English examination. 12 respondents, representing

66.7% agreed while 2 respondents representing 11.1% disagree.

Discussion of Results

The findings have shown that, there are availability of instructional materials or resources in teaching and learning of English in Okene Local Government Area secondary

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schools in Kogi state. 15 respondents representing 83.3% in table 19 agreed that chalkboard, charts, textbooks are available for teaching tenses, concord, essay writing and passage reading. In table 20 where 12 respondents representing 66.7% agreed that models, pictures and real objects are available for teaching English, 12 respondents representing 66.7% in table 18 disagreed that language laboratory or audio tape is available for teaching oral.

The researcher observed that only two schools out of the selected six confidentiality have language laboratories or audio tapes for teaching oral English. Other schools, especially the government schools, have only charts, chalkboard, textbooks, real objects and pictures for teaching English.

Also, from the interview, it was observed that the government provided materials or facilities for teaching English. However due to epileptic power supply in the environment, all the materials are not implemented when teaching English. Also, laziness of English teachers in public schools make the schools not to have enough charts an improvised model for teaching English language in view of this, the researcher concludes students' poor performance in English to be as a result lack of the availability of instructional materials and poor utilization of instructional materials by English teacher.

From the analyzed data, the responses from the teachers and students show that 8 teacher respondents representing 44.4% often use instructional materials while 10 teacher

respondents representing 55.6% sparingly use instructional materials in teaching English. 75 students out of the 86 student respondents representing 87.2% in table 5 agreed that their teachers use instructional materials. However, from the observation and interview, the materials generally available are chalkboards and textbooks while charts are only used by teachers on training. The research also discovered from her interaction with the students in government schools that their performance in English is poor. That is, wrong use of tenses, concord and grammar. This also is shown in their responses in of the administered questionnaire as some misinterpreted of questions.

According to Ozordi (2010), the factors that are responsible for students' failure in English are: failure to follow instructions, misunderstanding and misinterpretation of questions, poor spelling, illegible handwriting and poor grammatical expression and ignorance of rudiments of English Teachers are enjoin to adopt different strategies an always use instructional materials to help the pupils understanding in English.

Offorma (2002), points out that, as the learner makes effort to recall what committed to memory, he or she becomes frustrated and demotivated as there is no fun or Joy in the language class. Learners turn out to be "grammarians" rather than "linguists". This is because of lack or sparing use of instructional materials for and in teaching English.

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

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The findings also show the contribution of instructional materials to academic performance as 16 teachers in table 27 representing 88.9% strongly agreed and, agreed that pupils taught English with instructional materials perform better in any English examination than those taught with traditional methods. In table 28, 16 respondents representing 88.9% strongly agreed and agreed that those taught English with traditional method will hardly have credit pass in English. In support of this view, Ogundele (1987) Considered teaching aids as 'an essential part of teaching methods which helps the teacher to express the subject matter and concept to the learners, thus, improving students' performance. In table 14, 74 students representing 86% respondents strongly agreed and agreed that they perform better in any examination due to the aids of instructional materials stile in table 13, 70 students representing 81.4% respondents strongly agreed and agreed that their teachers' competence in English determine their performance. According to Salandanan (2005), competent teachers are imbued with values, attitudes and disposition that foster a classroom atmosphere of mutual trust for individual characteristics especially students' needs, interest and abilities. With no doubt, teachers' competence precede students' academic performance in English.

Significance of instructional materials cannot be undermined. Based on the findings, 70 students representing 81.4% in table 6 agreed that the use of instructional materials for classroom instruction boost their cognitive abilities while in

table 8, 79 students representing 91.9% said usage of instructional materials enhance their acquisition and retention of information in English. Wales (1975) also support this by saying that the use of instructional materials would make discovered facts glue firmly to the memory of students. 12 teachers representing 66.7% respondents also agreed that instructional materials make students acquire and retain information in English. Also 14 teachers representing 77.8% support the use of instructional materials for classroom instructions to boost the cognitive abilities of students. According to Ekwueme and Igwe (2001), a teacher who makes use of appropriate instructional materials to supplement his teaching will enhance students' innovative and creative thinking and as well help them become enthusiastic.

Based on the findings, English is better taught and learnt with the aids of instructional materials. 13 teachers representing 72.2% respondents in table 24 enjoy searching English with instructional materials, while in table 23, 15 respondents representing 83.3% agreed that instructional materials make teaching activities easy, lively and concrete.

Adewale (2011) said that instructional materials help the teacher to hold student's attention in the class. Similarly, Ugwu (2008) added that, instructional materials help teachers to control the pace of learning. It helps to make teaching learning meaningful.

The students also agree that they enjoy studying English with instructional material of as shown

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

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in table 10 where 78 respondents representing 90.7% were in support and in table 7 where 79 respondents representing 91.9% agreed that usage of instructional materials makes learning easy, lively and concrete. Since teaching-learning, according to Fakomogbon (2000), possesses the quality of influencing the psychological, motivational and structural position of learner, teaching and learning will be easier, lively and concrete with the use of instructional materials, hence, promoting teachers and student's performance in English.

In table 25, 11 teachers representing 61.1% respondents said improvement in English classroom instruction depends on teacher's competence. In table 26, 13 teachers representing 72.2% respondents agreed that teachers' competence and instructional materials determine the improvement in English classroom instruction. Orumbata (2011) agreed that instructional materials help teachers in improving their skills and broaden their knowledge; and since the objective of instructional materials in National Policy in Education is to improve the competences of teachers, however, teacher's competence and instructional materials works together for effective English teaching.

Students also agree, that instructional materials improve their reading and speaking capacity. In table 9, 77 respondents representing 89.5% said illustration through instructional materials improve their knowledge towards a topic in English. In support of this, Richard (2010) opines that instructional materials do not only

enable students to speak and write accurate grammar, but also help them to speak fluent unrehearsed English.

In conclusion, the use of instructional material is not a waste of time. This is because the little that is taught is assimilated and can easily be recalled, also it helps the learner to relate what is taught to life experience which perfect and make them a change being in their society.

This chapter deals with the summary, conclusion of effects of the use of instructional materials on students' academic performance in English in selected secondary schools in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State. Recommendations was given by the researcher. Limitation of the study and suggestions for further studies were discussed.

Summary

This study examines effects of the use of instructional materials on academic performance of secondary school students in English. The concept of English Language and its importance as well as students' poor performance in English was looked into. Concept of instructional materials and improvisation are studied.

Six research questions were raised and questions were developed to provide answer to the research questions. From the result of the findings it could be deduced the instructional materials and resources are available for the teaching and learning of English. It was revealed in table 18,19, 20 respectively. 15 respondents representing 83.3% in table 19 agree that charts, chalkboard, textbooks are available while in table 20, 66.7%

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

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respondents also said pictures, and real objects are available for teaching English. And, the question, on if teachers use instructional materials in the process of teaching English language, we answered in table 5 as 87.2% respondents agreed that their teachers use instructional materials for teaching English.

The findings show the significance of instructional materials on students' performance in English. In table 22, 66.7% respondents support that instructional material enhance students' acquisition and retention of information. Similarly, table 6 shows 81.4% respondents said when instructional materials are used for classroom instruction, their cognitive abilities improve. Therefore, instructional materials contribute greatly to the performance of students in English. That is, pupils taught English with instructional materials perform excellently in any English examination than those that are taught with traditional method as shown in table 27, 16 respondents representing 88.9% strongly agree and agreed.

However, English Language in better taught and learnt with the aids of instructional materials as majority agree that instructional materials make teaching and wing activities easy, lively, and concrete in table 10 and 24,07% 72.2 respectively said they enjoy learning and teaching activities with the aids of instructional material. The findings show that improvement of students' academic performance depend largely on teacher's competent and instruction materials as 72.2% respondents are in support of the view.

Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

Conclusion

Educational attainment depends on the quality of teaching. The findings of this study reveal that there is lack of adequate and efficient instructional materials or resources especially in government established secondary schools, 66.7% of the respondents in table 18 said language laboratory or radio tapes are not available for teaching oral English. It can be concluded that the only available materials are chalkboards, textbooks and charts of which must of the English teachers do not use. And improvement of students' academic performance in English demand the use of instructional materials by competent teachers. However, there is a need for effective and efficient inclusion of instructional materials in the school's system for better teaching strategy and as such ensure high academic performance of students in English.

Recommendations

If the purpose of English is to be achieved as well as student's excellent performance in English is to be attained at all educational levels in Nigeria, certain must be considered to enhance effective and efficiency teaching and learning process. The measures are as follows:

More seminars or workshops on the use of diverse instructional materials available should be organize to acquaint teachers on how to use instructional materials in teaching English.

- School administration should ensure that instructional materials are provided for teachers to enhance effective teaching of English.

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- Teachers and students should form the habit of improvising instructional materials to make up the shortfall in supply.
- Teachers should apply special knowledge and skills with respect to selecting, and using different kinds of instructional materials.
- Enough time should be allotted in the schools' time table for effective use of instructional materials in English classroom.
- A committee should be set up in educational sector to monitor teachers' use of instructional materials in teaching English.
- Educational managers should ensure that English teachers have educational qualification in English as a way of acquainting them with the principle and administration of instructional materials in secondary schools.

Limitation of the Study

In carrying out the research, a lot of challenges were encountered by the researcher which led to limitation in the study. The researcher selected five schools in four town in Okene Local Government Area, Kogi State because of financial constraint and the bad road.

In administering the questionnaire to the respondents, the teachers are not ready to devote their time in giving vital information for this study and as such reject the questionnaire. The students, despite the instruction and guidance fill the questionnaire wrongly.

The researcher should have investigated more than six schools and four towns for this study, but, because of the time limit and risk involved limit the study to six school and four towns.

Suggestion for Further Studies

Based on the light of above discussions, the researcher therefore suggests further researcher to based their research; On teacher's competence and instructional materials as an instrument of students' performance in English; Comparing private schools' performance with public schools performance in English using instructional material.

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Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani

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Jimoh, Isiaka Odiyani